

The impact of maternal supplementation of fish oil and/or probiotics during pregnancy on the serum metabolomic profile from infancy to childhood: secondary analysis of a randomized placebo-controlled trial

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An alphabetized list of abbreviations and their definitions for all non-standard abbreviations used in the text: branched chain amino acids, BCAA; cholesteryl esters, CE; DHA, docosahexaenoic acid; EPA, eicosapentaenoic acid; FDR, false discovery rate; free

cholesterol, FC; GDM, gestational diabetes mellitus; GLMM, generalized linear mixed model; intermediate density lipoprotein, IDL; IQR, interquartile range; large, L; medium, M; multi-omics factor analysis 2, MOFA2; NMR, nuclear magnetic resonance; n-3 LC-PUFA, n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids; Permutational Analysis of Variance, PERMANOVA; phospholipids, PL; principal coordinate analysis, PCA; total lipids, L; small, S; triglycerides, TG, very large, XL; extremely large, XXL, very small, XS

ABSTRACT

Background: Probiotics and fish oil may modify metabolism, but the extent to which their impacts can be transferred from mother to child is unknown.

Objective: To unravel the impact of perinatal exposure to fish oil and/or probiotics on the serum metabolomic profile in early childhood.

Methods: Children (n=300) of pregnant women receiving fish oil+placebo, probiotics+placebo, fish oil+probiotics or placebo+placebo (fish oil: 1.9g docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and 0.2 g eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA); probiotics: *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* HN001 and *Bifidobacterium animalis* ssp. *lactis* 420) from early pregnancy to 6-months postpartum were followed-up until 5–6 years of age. The children serum metabolomic profiles were analysed using nuclear magnetic resonance metabolomics. The intervention's impact on the overall metabolomic profile was tested using permutation analysis of variance with multi-omics factor analysis (MOFA2) utilized to identify out the sources of variability within each group, followed by a univariate comparison between the intervention groups at each age. The time-effect was analyzed using a mixed model.

Results: The maternal intervention changed the concentrations of fatty acids and lipoproteins of the 6-month-old children (FDR<0.05). The main effects included higher serum concentration of DHA and n-3 fatty acids, a higher ratio of n-3/n-6 fatty acids in fish oil+placebo and fish oil+probiotics groups compared with placebo+placebo, along with higher concentrations of lipids and cholesterol derivatives in very large high-density lipoproteins (HDL). Probiotics alone did not

affect the serum metabolites. At 1, 2 and 5-6 years, twenty-four metabolites were affected by the intervention but after multiple correction, none of these remained statistically significant.

Conclusions: Maternal intervention with fish oil alone and in combination with probiotics induces alterations in the metabolic profile at 6 months of age, as demonstrated by increased circulating n-3 fatty acids and lipids in HDL. Perinatal modulation of maternal diet may represent one way to improve the offspring's metabolism.

Clinical Trial Registry number: NCT01922791

(<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT01922791>).

Keywords: Childhood, Infancy, Metabolomics, Pregnancy, Fish oil, Probiotics, RCT, Longitudinal

Teaser text

Maternal fish oil, with or without probiotics elevated child's blood n-3 fatty acids and HDL lipids at 6 months. These effects faded by age 6. Probiotics alone showed no impact.

INTRODUCTION

A child's metabolism is of critical importance, not only in regulating her/his growth and development, but also influencing the risk of diseases, extending up to adulthood. It is noteworthy that these regulatory processes may be influenced already during the intrauterine period (1). Therefore, disruptions in maternal metabolic health during pregnancy, such as may occur with overweight and obesity, may be of importance and have detrimental effects on the fetus's metabolic regulation (2). In this regard, it has been claimed that the perinatal stage serves as an ideal time-window to modify maternal exposures such that they will induce beneficial metabolic changes in the fetus, and subsequently promote the child's development and future health (3).

As we have previously reported, a supplementation of combined fish oil and probiotics during pregnancy induced alterations in circulating compounds related to lipid, glucose and amino acid metabolism (3) as well as in the composition of the gut microbiota (4). Both fish oil and probiotics possess beneficial properties, i.e., fish oil, which is rich in n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-3 LC-PUFA), in particular docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), is known to alleviate metabolic perturbations, like insulin resistance and cardiovascular outcomes (5,6) by reducing inflammation and improving lipid metabolism (7) as well as being beneficial to the development of the fetal visual and central-nervous system (8). Administration of probiotics, like *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus* has also been

shown to influence lipid homeostasis, via a regulation of the gut microbiota and inflammation (9). The effects of these supplements can potentially be enhanced by their combination. For example, the administration of n-3 LC-PUFA with probiotics caused a more profound effect on the lipid content of lipoproteins of mothers with overweight and obesity than either supplement alone (3).

Importantly, although the maternal intake of fish oil and probiotics during pregnancy did not influence the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus (10), it may evoke cross-generational effects, as evidenced by a reduced risk for overweight and obesity and recurrent wheezing in their two-year-old children(11,12). Here, high-throughput metabolomics was utilized to clarify the metabolic mechanisms behind the health implications of in-utero exposures of maternal metabolism and dietary factors. This approach has made it possible to pinpoint specific metabolic processes and fluxes in the first years of life in childhood (13). In a previous study, maternal supplementation of n-3 LC-PUFA from mid-pregnancy to one-week postpartum reduced the levels of metabolites related to fatty acids (n-6 LC-PUFAs, monosaturated and saturated fatty acids) and tryptophan while there were higher levels of metabolites related to tyrosine and glutamic acid in children at the age of 4–8 months (14). Thus far, the research is scarce, and no studies exist on the combined administration of n-3 LC-PUFA and probiotics in a longitudinal setting from pregnancy until 6 years of age. While the impact of maternal health and nutrition on the child's later health is acknowledged, the metabolic processes in early childhood induced by specific nutritional exposure during pregnancy have remained unexplored. Furthermore, while the use of metabolomic approaches in the context of pediatrics is making progress,

longitudinal dietary studies from early infancy to later childhood are limited, and none have involved mother-child pairs with the focus on perinatal and postnatal fish oil and probiotic exposure. Metabolic processes in early life could also act as potential mechanisms between maternal fish oil and/or probiotics intervention and various conditions. Therefore, we aimed to investigate the influence of maternal supplementation of fish oil or/and probiotics during pregnancy and 6-month postpartum on the metabolomic profile of children as they grew from 6 months to 5–6 years of age.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and subjects

This study utilizes data from a double-blinded randomized placebo-controlled single-center intervention with fish oil and/or probiotic supplementation (ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT01922791) for which women were recruited in Southwest Finland between October 2013 and July 2017. The original trial design has previously been described in detail, and the primary outcomes were to investigate if fish oil and/or probiotics supplements decrease the risk of GDM in women and allergies in children (10).

Briefly, a total of 439 pregnant women were enrolled into the study and randomized to the intervention. Pregnant women (gestational weeks < 18) were eligible with BMI ≥ 25 kg/m², and who did not present with multifetal pregnancy, gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) diagnosis and metabolic or inflammatory diseases. Here, our interest was to investigate the influence of maternal fish oil and/or probiotics supplementation

on the metabolomic profile of their children that is a predefined secondary outcome of the original trial, up to 5–6 years of age.

Demographics (age, education, smoking habits) were collected by interviewing the participants who filled in questionnaires during the first study visit in early pregnancy. Information on delivery was obtained from hospital medical records. Pre-pregnancy BMI (kg/m^2) was determined by dividing self-reported pre-pregnancy weight obtained from health clinic records by height measured with a wall stadiometer to the nearest 0.1 cm at the first study visit.

The children of the participating women were followed-up to 5 to 6 years of age. In this present study, a blood sample from a total of 257 children at 6 months, 256 at 1 year, 238 at 2 years and 83 at 5 to 6 years of age was available for metabolomics analysis (**Figure 1**). Information regarding the child's health and growth measurements was obtained from hospital and pediatric health clinic medical records. Children's birth and growth data consisting of weight-for-length% and -height%, weight for age SD scores as well as weight, height and head circumference were determined as previously described (12). The duration of breastfeeding and the use of infant formula (until the age of 2 years) were assessed during the follow-up visits orally and via questionnaires. The parents of the children filled in 3-day food diaries on behalf of the children at the age of 2 and 5–6-years. The study followed the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki, and the Ethics Committee of the Hospital District of Southwest Finland gave a prior approval for the study protocol before the

study commenced. All mothers provided written informed consent and children of the age of 5–6 years.

Intervention

The women were randomized in a double-blind manner into four groups: 1) fish oil+placebo, 2) probiotics+placebo, 3) fish oil+probiotics, and 4) placebo+placebo at the first study visit (13.9 ± 2.1 gestational weeks). The allocation was conducted according to the women's parity and history of GDM. The fish oil capsules contained 2.4 g of n–3 LC-PUFA (1.9 g DHA, 0.22 EPA, and 0.28 g other n–3 fatty acids, e.g., docosapentaenoic acid; Croda Europe Ltd., Leek, UK) and the probiotic capsules contained 10^{10} colony-forming units of *Lacticaseibacillus* (formerly *Lactobacillus*) *rhamnosus* HN001 (ATCC SD5675; DuPont, Niebull, Germany) and *Bifidobacterium animalis* ssp. lactis 420 (DSM 22089; DuPont) per capsule. The placebo for fish oil contained an equal amount of medium-chain fatty acids as the fish oil capsules, and the placebo for the probiotics contained microcrystalline cellulose with an identical shape, size and color as the active capsule. Women were instructed to consume two fish oil and one probiotic capsule throughout the intervention from the first study visit until 6 months of postpartum. The intervention with fish oil and/or probiotics during pregnancy were both safe and well tolerated (10). The overall study compliance was 88.4% based on the returned fish oil capsules. The mean individual compliance was $91.8\% \pm 15.9$ (10). This has been further confirmed when nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) determined the serum lipids of the mothers guaranteeing their fish oil intake (3).

Blood sampling and metabolomics analysis

Blood samples of the children at the age of 6 months, 1, and 2 years were withdrawn from antecubital vein after a varying time of eating (1.50 h [interquartile range (IQR) 1.00, 2.00] at 6 months, n=225; 1.50 h [IQR 1.00, 2.00] at 1 year, n=227; 2.00 h [1.50, 2.50] at 2 years, n=87), and after an overnight fast at the age of 5–6 years of age (10.5 h [2.57, 7.71], n=49) by a certified nurse with experience in pediatrics. The serum was separated and stored in aliquots at -80 degrees until the analysis. The serum metabolites were determined using a high-throughput NMR metabolomics platform (Nightingale Health Ltd, Helsinki, Finland) as previously described (15). The platform consists of a targeted set of 250 metabolite biomarkers of lipid and glucose metabolism, amino acids, ketone bodies and glycoprotein acetyls. The bioinformatic analyses were carried out separately for 173 metabolites analysed as concentrations and ratio of n-6/n-3 fatty acids, and for 77 metabolites analysed as the ratio of total lipids or total fatty acids. The missing values in metabolite data were imputed using *impute_metabimpute_gsimp()* function from *imputomics* R package (v0.1.3).

Statistical and bioinformatics analysis

The statistical analysis for the clinical characteristics in four diet intervention groups was carried out in R (v4.4.2) (16). The normality of distribution of the continuous data was visually observed from histograms and statistically evaluated by Shapiro-Wilk test. Normally distributed data were described as means with standard deviations, skewed data as medians with interquartile ranges and categorical data as

frequencies with percentages. Statistical differences were tested to evaluate global differences in diet intervention. One-Way Analysis of Variance was used for normally distributed continuous variables and Kruskal-Wallis for skewed variables. Categorical variables were compared using Pearson chi-square or Fisher's exact test. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant for clinical outcomes.

The study was originally powered according to the primary outcome of GDM incidence and allergy in the study children (10). In the present study, the metabolomic profile was a predefined secondary outcome. The power for the effect of the intervention on the child's metabolomics analysis could not be calculated since during the time of intervention, the application of a metabolomics approach to study human metabolism was only just emerging, and no prior data on the effects of maternal supplementation of fish oil and/or probiotics on child serum metabolomics existed. Nevertheless, the number of study participants was considered sufficient to detect differences in serum metabolites in response to the intervention, as reported previously in mothers (3,17).

The dissimilarities in the metabolomic profile were assessed with miaViz (v1.16.0) (18). The data was log₁₀-transformed using pseudocount (equal to minimum non-zero value) then z-score normalized across features. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed on transformed data and global group differences were evaluated using Permutational Analysis of Variance (PERMANOVA) statistical comparison. Multi-Omics Factor Analysis 2 (MOFA2) multi-group framework analysis

(v1.16.0) (19) was used to identify the sources of variability in the metabolomic profile within each intervention group and to characterize shared patterns across groups and to identify which are specific to individual group. To test for differential abundance, two complementary methods were used. First, using DAtest R package (v2.8.0), we applied the non-parametric approach (20). Then, the Kruskal-Wallis-test with Benjamini-Hochberg method to control for the False Discovery Rate (FDR) for multiple comparisons was applied to evaluate the global differences between the intervention groups followed by post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Mann-Whitney U-test with Bonferroni correction and Benjamini-Hochberg method. An $FDR < 0.05$ was considered as a statistically significant. Both Bonferroni and FDR-adjusted p-values are reported. A heatmap of pairwise significant metabolites was generated using log₂ fold change values which were normalized by Median Absolute Deviation (MAD). Secondly, we used MaAsLin2 (v1.19.0) (21) determine the associations between intervention groups and the children's metabolic profile with log-transformation and TSS normalization. The model was adjusted with confounding factors, maternal prepregnancy BMI, smoking during pregnancy because these variables differed between the intervention groups at the age of 6 months (see **Supplementary Table 1**). The child's sex was also considered in the model since sex is known to influence the metabolomic profile in early childhood (22,23). To examine the effect of the diet intervention across age, we used a generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) with Gamma distribution and log link function. The model included the fixed effects for interaction between diet intervention group and age, and a random intercept for each subject. The fixed-effect structure was aligned with

covariates used in MaAsLin2 analysis, which includes maternal prepregnancy BMI, smoking during pregnancy and child sex. All visualizations were created using ggplot2 (v3.5.1) (24), ggpubr (v0.60) (25), and patchwork (v1.3.0) (26)

RESULTS

Maternal and child characteristics

The characteristics of the mothers and birth data of the children in relation to the intervention are presented in **Table 1**. More than half of the mothers were living with overweight (62.0%, $25 \leq \text{BMI} < 30$), while the rest were living with obesity (38.0%, $\text{BMI} \geq 30$). Most of the births were via vaginal delivery (84.0%), and half of the children were girls (50.0%). With respect to the intervention groups, smoking during pregnancy differed between the intervention groups ($p < 0.002$), being highest in the placebo+placebo group (26.0%). Further characteristics of the children at the age of 6 months, and further at 1 year, 2 and 5–6 years of age in relation to the intervention are presented in the **Supplementary Table 1**.

The impact of maternal supplementation with fish oil and/or probiotics on the global child serum metabolomic profile at different ages

No statistically significant separation (PERMANOVA) between dietary intervention groups at any of the examined ages, 6 months ($p = 0.11$), 1 year ($p = 0.66$), 2 years ($p = 0.26$), and 5–6 years ($p = 0.87$), was visible in PCA, **Figure 2**. This indicates that the global metabolomic differences between groups were subtle and could not

be shown in the unsupervised PCA visualization (PCA loadings are presented in **Supplementary Figure 1**).

To further explore age-specific patterns in metabolite-driven variation, MOFA2 was applied using a multi-group framework (concentrations and ratios separately and dietary intervention groups were considered as groups and age groups as views). With respect to the concentrations, at the age of 6 months and 1 year, fish oil+placebo group exhibited the highest variance (33% and 26%, respectively) while at 2 years and 5–6 years the probiotics+placebo exhibited the highest variance (30% and 15%, respectively) (**Figure 3a, Supplementary Table 2**). A declining trend in total variance was observed with increasing age, with the lowest variance noted in the children aged 5–6 years (8-15%), and with the lowest variance being in the placebo+placebo group. Furthermore, Factor 1 captured the largest proportion of variance across samples, as expected from the MOFA model, which orders the latent factors according to a decreasing explanatory power. The Factor 1 variance of concentrations of metabolites was highest in the fish oil+placebo group at the age of 6 months (20%), 1 year (17%) and 5–6 years (9%) while in the probiotics+placebo group, it occurred at 2 years (17%). (**Figure 3b, Supplementary Table 2**). In all ages, the Factor 1 variance was driven primarily by total fatty acids (**Figure 3c, Supplementary Table 2**)

With respect to ratios, when we examined the total variance at 6 months and 1 year of age, the fish oil+placebo group exhibited the highest variance (93% at both ages) while at 2 and 5–6 years, the placebo+placebo group displayed the highest variance (93% and 56% respectively) (**Supplementary Figure 2a, Supplementary Table 3**).

The highest Factor 1 variance was evident in the fish oil+probiotics group at age 6 months (56%), in the placebo+placebo group at the age of 1 year (59%), 2 years (54%) and 5–6 years (38%) (**Supplementary Figure 2b, Supplementary Table 3**). At 6 months, 1 year and 2 years, the majority of Factor 1 variance was driven by the ratio of triacylglycerols to total lipids in extremely large VLDL while at 5–6 of age, it was attributable to the ratio of cholesterol to total lipids in extremely large VLDL (**Supplementary Figure 2b Supplementary Table 3**). Overall, ratios of metabolites related to VLDL lipoproteins emerged as the primary contributor to the variation across all age groups.

The impact of maternal intervention on serum metabolomics in 6-month-old children

At the age of 6 months, the maternal dietary intervention was associated with significant changes in the concentrations of 25 metabolites, as identified using the Kruskal-Wallis multi-group test ($p < 0.05$). Of these, 9 metabolites remained statistically significant after correction for multiple testing (Kruskal-Wallis, $FDR < 0.05$; **Supplementary Table 4**). Namely, the concentrations of fatty acids, DHA and n-3 fatty acids (sum of DHA, EPA and α -linolenic acid), and the degree of unsaturation of fatty acids (the number of carbon-carbon double bonds in the fatty acid carbon chain) were higher while the ratio of n-6 to n-3 fatty acids was lower in both the fish oil+placebo and the fish oil+probiotics groups as compared to the placebo+placebo and probiotics+placebo groups (Mann-Whitney with Bonferroni correction and Benjamini-Hochberg method, $FDR < 0.05$; **Figure 4; Supplementary Table 5**). With respect to the lipoproteins, the composition of very large HDL, namely, cholesterol,

cholesteryl esters (CE), free cholesterol (FC), phospholipids (PL) and total lipids in the particles was significantly higher in the fish oil+placebo and fish oil+probiotics groups in comparison to placebo+placebo (Mann-Whitney with Bonferroni correction and Benjamini-Hochberg method, $FDR < 0.05$; **Figure 4; Supplementary Table 5**).

These metabolites, but not PL in very large HDL, were also higher in the children of the participants in the fish oil+placebo and fish oil+probiotics groups as compared to those whose mothers had received probiotics+placebo (Mann-Whitney with Bonferroni correction and Benjamini-Hochberg method, $FDR < 0.05$ **Figure 4; Supplementary Table 5**). Nonetheless, total lipids were not affected by the consumption of fish oil+placebo when compared to probiotics+placebo. There were no significant differences in the comparison of fish oil+placebo to fish oil+probiotics, nor of probiotics+placebo to placebo+placebo (Mann-Whitney with Bonferroni correction and Benjamini-Hochberg method, $FDR < 0.05$, **Figure 4; Supplementary Table 5**). In a multivariate model adjusted for the child's sex, maternal prepregnancy BMI and smoking during pregnancy, the interventions involving fish oil+placebo and fish oil+probiotics were associated with an increased abundance in the concentration of DHA, and the fish oil+probiotics intervention with an elevated abundance of n-3 fatty acids, as well as very large HDL and reduced ratio of n-6/n-3 fatty acids and (MaAslin2 $FDR < 0.05$) (MaAsLin2, $FDR < 0.05$) (**Supplementary Table 5**). Finally, the maternal consumption of probiotics+placebo did not seem to exert any impact on the serum metabolomics in the offspring.

In terms of the metabolites analysed as total lipid and total fatty acids ratios, the maternal dietary intervention was associated with statistically significant changes in

the ratios of 30 metabolites at the age of 6 months, as identified using the Kruskal-Wallis multi-group test ($p < 0.05$). Of these, 7 metabolites, including lipid ratios related to n-3 fatty acids and the lipid composition of HDL and LDL particles differed statistically between the groups (Kruskal-Wallis FDR < 0.05 ; **Supplementary Table 7**). Namely, in the group-wise comparisons, the following ratios were significantly changed; higher ratios were detected for n-3 fatty acids and DHA to total fatty acids, PL to total lipids in medium LDL and small LDL and FC to total lipids in small HDL while lower ratios were evident for PL to total lipids in large HDL and CE to total lipids in medium LDL in the fish oil+placebo and fish oil+probiotics when compared to the placebo+placebo group. (Mann-Whitney with Bonferroni correction and Benjamini-Hochberg method, FDR < 0.05 ; **Supplementary Table 8**). The results were essentially the same in the fish oil+placebo versus probiotics+placebo comparisons, but two ratios i.e., PL to total lipids in small LDL and PL to total lipids in large HDL did not differ between the groups. Similarly, the comparisons between fish oil+probiotics and probiotics+placebo group revealed that the results were essentially the same, with the exception of the ratio of CE to total lipids in medium LDL and the PL to total lipids ratio in large HDL, which did not differ between the groups. There were no differences between probiotics+placebo as compared to placebo+placebo or fish oil+placebo when compared to fish oil+probiotics (Mann-Whitney with Bonferroni correction and Benjamini-Hochberg method, FDR < 0.05 ; **Supplementary Table 8**). In the multivariate model adjusted for covariates, increases in n-3 fatty acids and DHA to total fatty acids ratio were present in the fish oil+placebo group as was the DHA to

total fatty acids ratio in the fish oil+probiotics group (MaAslin2, FDR<0.05)

(Supplementary Table 9)

The impact of the maternal intervention on the serum metabolomics of 1-, 2- and 5–6-year-old children

At the age of 1 year, in the initial inspection, a total of 18 metabolites were assessed as having been influenced by the maternal intervention (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.05$)

(Supplementary Table 4). These metabolites included amino acids, lipoproteins, lipids, and metabolites related to energy metabolism, but none remained significant after multiple testing (Kruskal-Wallis, $FDR > 0.05$). At the age of 2 years, in the initial inspection, while it did seem that the creatine level had been significantly influenced by the interventions in two-year-old children (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.05$), after multiple testing correction, this difference disappeared (Kruskal-Wallis, $FDR < 0.05$)

(Supplementary Table 4). At the age of 5–6 years, in the initial univariate statistical analysis, five metabolites, i.e., lactate, pyruvate, alanine, triglycerides in large LDL and intermediate density lipoprotein (IDL) particles, appeared to have been influenced by the intervention, (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.05$), but once again, none remained significant after correcting for multiple testing (Kruskal-Wallis, $FDR < 0.05$) **(Supplementary Table 4)**. Furthermore, none of the associations were significant in the multivariate model after adjustment with prepregnancy BMI, smoking and child sex when correcting for multiple testing in any of the age groups (MaAslin2, $FDR > 0.05$) **(Supplementary Table 6)**.

When individual metabolites were analysed as the ratio of one metabolite to the total, then there were changes in the ratio of PL to total lipids in large LDL at the age of 1

year. While it seemed that there were also changes with respect to seven metabolites which had been influenced by the maternal intervention, i.e., the ratio of PL, cholesterol, CE and TG to total lipids in different lipoproteins at the age of 2 years and 6 metabolites, including the ratio of PL, cholesterol, CE, FC and TG to total lipids in different lipoproteins at the age of 5–6 (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.05$), these differences were no longer statistically significant after correction for multiple testing (Kruskal-Wallis, $FDR > 0.05$; **Supplementary Table 7**). In the multivariate model analyses, none of the ratios of the metabolites to total lipids or total fatty acids were statistically significant in any of the age groups (MaAslin2, $FDR > 0.05$) (**Supplementary Tables 9**).

The impact of maternal intervention on serum metabolites of children from 6 months to 5–6 years of age

We further investigated the change in selected metabolites (statistically significant according to Kruskal-Wallis in the multi-group testing) across the time-points and intervention groups using linear regression models adjusted with covariates. With respect to the concentrations, overall those of DHA and n-3 fatty acids decreased along with age while the n-6/n-3 fatty acid ratio as well as the lipids in very large HDL increased when the children grew from being babes to young children (**Figure 5**). The statistically significant time x group interaction effects ($FDR < 0.05$, **Figure 5 heatmap**), indicated that the provision to the mothers of probiotics+placebo did not have any effect on the children's metabolite concentrations whereas the metabolites with the exception of the n-6/n-3 fatty acid ratios, increased more in the fish

oil+placebo and fish oil+probiotics groups as compared to the placebo+placebo group (**Figure 5 heatmap**).

Similarly, when the calculation was conducted in terms of ratios, there were declines in the ratios of 1) PL to total fatty acids in large HDL, 2) CE to total lipids in medium LDL, 3) n-3 fatty acids to total fatty acids; in contrast, the ratio of PL to total lipids in medium LDL increased (**Supplementary Figure 3**). Interestingly, the ratio of DHA to total fatty acids as well as that of FC to total lipids in small HDL decreased from 6 months until 2 years and then fluctuated until 5–6 years. Furthermore, the ratio PL to total lipids in small LDL increased from 6 months until 1 year and then exhibited a decreasing trend as the children aged to 5–6 years. An examination of the statistically significant time x group interaction revealed that probiotics+placebo did not have an effect on the metabolite ratios whereas the ratio of DHA and n-3 fatty acids to total fatty acids and the ratio of FC to total lipids in small HDL decreased more from 6 months until 5–6 years in the participants in two groups i.e., in the fish oil+placebo and fish oil+probiotics groups as compared to the placebo+placebo group (FDR<0.05, **Supplementary Figure 3, heatmap**). In the fish oil+probiotics group, the ratio of PL to total lipids in large HDL increased more from 6 months to 5–6 years as compared to placebo. Changes in shorter period of times were detected in the fish oil+placebo and fish oil+probiotics groups; in the fish oil+placebo group, the ratio of PL to total lipids in large HDL increased more until 2 years. Similarly, the ratio of CE to total lipids in medium LDL increased more until 1 year while the ratio of PL to total lipids in medium LDL exhibited a greater decrease more until the children were 1 year than in the placebo+placebo group. Finally, the ratio of CE in total lipids

increased more until the children's first birthday in the fish oil+probiotics group in comparison to the placebo+placebo group.

DISCUSSION

Our findings demonstrate that supplementation of the maternal diet with fish oil and/or probiotics from early pregnancy to 6 months postpartum represents a potential mechanism for the previous clinical findings (11,12) and a means of influencing the child's serum metabolomic profile up to 5–6 years of age, with the largest differences being evident at 6 months of age. The global inspection (PCA) of the intervention effect revealed no differences between the intervention groups but all the intervention groups contributed to the variance of the metabolic profile with a decreasing trend over time (MOFA). The detailed inspection of the differences between the groups per time-point revealed that fish oil and fish oil in combination with probiotics but not probiotics alone had influenced the metabolites at the age of 6 months. Namely, the children of mothers who had been supplemented with fish oil alone and in combination with probiotics had higher circulating levels of n–3 fatty acids, along with a higher concentration of metabolites related to lipoprotein metabolism. This was evident with respect to the very large subfractions of HDL as defined by differences in the density of different lipids (CE, FC, PL and total lipids). Furthermore, time-interaction analyses showed that those same metabolites except the ratio of n-6/n-3 fatty acids decreased in the fish oil+placebo and fish oil+probiotics groups as compared to the placebo+placebo group from 6 months to 5–6 years of age. In addition, the values describing the ratio of total lipids support these findings along

with revealing additional results on decreased CE and increased PL ratios with respect to total lipids in LDL particles in the participants consuming fish oil alone or in combination with probiotics.

In the present study, the maternal consumption of fish oil alone and in combination with probiotics was reflected in their offspring's serum lipid concentrations at the age of 6 months with especially, the concentrations of n-3 fatty acids being affected. The children were exposed to maternal fish oil supplementation as most of them were breast-fed until 6 months postpartum. Another route and time-window for the exposure would occur already during the fetal period; this proposal is supported from our earlier studies where we showed that the supplementation with fish oil increased the maternal serum concentrations of n-3 fatty acids during pregnancy (3,17). It is noteworthy that the combination of fish oil and probiotics as compared to placebo-induced effects altered a higher number of metabolites than fish oil alone in our previous study done in pregnant women (3) than was seen in this current study conducted with children. However, when the combination of fish oil and probiotics was compared to probiotics alone, it was observed that 13 metabolites differed statistically significantly between the groups but when the combination was compared to fish oil alone, then no differences were seen. Even though the fish oil+probiotics group did not differ statistically significantly from the fish oil+placebo group, the medians of the statistically significant metabolites at 6 months of age in fish oil+probiotics groups were higher than in fish oil+placebo group suggesting that the probiotics may have had some synergistic effects when combined with fish oil. Similarly to evidence emerging from our previous study, the combination of fish oil

and probiotics exerted effects in immune mediators in pregnant women not only when compared to fish oil alone, but also in the comparison with probiotics alone (27). It was shown in another study with maternal supplementation of fish oil containing 2.4 g n-3 LC-PUFA from weeks 22–26 of pregnancy but continuing only until 1 week postpartum that a distinctive plasma metabolic profile could be detected in the metabolome in children at the age of 6 months (14). Our study extended up to 5–6 years of age but differences in the metabolic profile were no longer detected at these later timepoints, reflecting the termination of the pregnancy intervention effect as well as the fact that in order to achieve stable concentrations of circulating serum fatty acids would require continual exposure to fish oil. This was supported by MOFA analysis, which suggests that the effects of this dietary intervention seemed to diminish with age. Interestingly, the group x time interaction analyses showed that the metabolites that differed between fish oil or fish oil+probiotics and placebo+placebo groups at 6 months of age, decreased or increased more until 5–6 years of age in these same groups than in placebo, an indication of longer lasting effects. Thus, the results may be interpreted to demonstrate that early life exposure to fish oil could be able to exert a long-lasting impact on metabolic regulation and health. This concept is supported by other studies in which early-life exposure to n-3 LC-PUFAs has had clinical benefits including a lower risk for asthma (28). Nonetheless, the impacts of the maternal intake of n-3 LC-PUFAs for the cardiometabolic health of the child have been contradictory. The children of mothers receiving fish oil on a daily basis during pregnancy from week 24 until 1 week after birth presented with a higher BMI at 6 years of age (29), and later the same children

seemed to have an increased risk for being overweight at 10 years of age as compared to the control group of children of mothers who consumed olive oil containing n-9 oleic acid and n-6 linoleic acid (30). On the contrary, if the n-3 LC-PUFA supplementation was given to infants from birth to 6 months of age, when the children reached 5 years of age, the effects were beneficial i.e., a lower waist circumference and reduced insulin resistance (31). The variations in the results could be explained by the different composition of n-3 LC-PUFAs administered, dosage and duration of intake, and the length of the follow-up.

As well as the n-3 fatty acids, the concentrations of CE, FC and PL in very large HDL particles were influenced in terms of whether the mothers consumed fish oil alone or fish oil in combination with probiotics i.e., those were increased by the intervention. We suggest that the intervention exerted beneficial effects also in this regard as previous studies conducted in children have shown that low lipid concentrations in large and very large HDL particles are associated with an increased type 2 diabetes liability in 8-, 16-, 18-, and 25-year-old subjects (32). This concept is supported by another study, where a small HDL particle size was associated with the presence of type 2 diabetes in children at the age of 12 years (33). Moreover, in one study, cardiorespiratory fitness was positively associated with the concentrations of large and extra-large HDL particles in 6–8-year-old children (34). When the amount of PL in the HDL particles was assessed, it was found that this correlated with an increased risk for cardiometabolic problems in 18-year-old female adolescents (35). In addition to the findings related to the HDL particles, we found effects in the LDL particles

when this was measured as a ratio to total lipids in the children who were 6 months of age; there were higher ratios of PL to total lipids in medium LDL and small LDL. In contrast, the ratio of CE to total lipids in medium LDL was lower when the children's mothers had been in either the fish oil+placebo or the fish oil+probiotics group rather than the placebo+placebo group. Since an increased level of CE in LDL is a well-known risk factor for cardiovascular diseases (36), the findings related to the lower CE to total lipids ratio in medium LDL after maternal consumption of either fish oil+placebo or fish oil+probiotics can be considered as beneficial. Similarly, the finding of a higher PL to total lipids ratio in medium and small LDL is in line with this above beneficial effect, i.e., when the ratio of PL to total lipids increases, the ratio of other major components, i.e., CE and TG, will decrease, both of which are known to exert detrimental effects on the body's metabolism. Regarding the effects of the probiotics, our findings from the group-wise comparisons per age in years and with a longitudinal inspection are in line with our previous finding (3,17) as the probiotics did not influence the metabolites in the children. Nonetheless, it is possible that probiotics may exert some effects in lipids as seen in the levels n-3 fatty acids in breast milk (37).

Interestingly, before controlling for multiple comparisons, it appeared that exposure to maternal supplementation alone had been able to influence the concentrations of serum branched chain amino acids (BCAA), isoleucine, leucine and valine, as well as one aromatic amino acid, phenylalanine, in 1-year-old children. As far as we are aware, we are the first to report that maternal intake of fish oil and/or probiotics would be able to alter the serum concentrations of BCAAs in toddlers in a mother-child pair

dietary intervention. Serum concentrations of BCAAs have been previously suggested to act as an indicator of hyperinsulinemia (38), and the concentrations of BCAAs in cord blood have been associated with adiposity in children (39). In particular, the leucine level in the newborn has been shown to predict overweight later in childhood (40). Thus, it could be argued that BCAAs could serve as a marker for metabolic processes and disease risks, rather than having a causal role in disease development but still requires further investigations.

The main strength of our study lies in the randomized controlled trial design with dietary supplementation in large mother-child-pair population, although the outcomes are secondary. In addition, this study has a long follow-up i.e., up to 5–6 years of age with a large number of serum samples gathered from the children. Unfortunately, rather many children dropped out during the follow-up, especially at the age of 5–6 years. In this respect, these results could suffer from a lack of power, and a larger sample size may be required if one wishes to detect statistically significant differences at the later ages. It is also noteworthy that the mothers were living with overweight or obesity, and thus, these findings may not be applicable to children of mothers with normal weight. However, we chose to study this group of women who not only themselves but also their children are at increased risk for developing metabolic diseases, as they represent an important group in which interventions may be beneficial.

These findings demonstrate that metabolism in childhood is affected by maternal dietary exposure as early as the fetal period. We observed beneficial effects in the infants such as an increase in concentrations of n–3 fatty acids and lipids in HDL and

LDL particles due to maternal supplementation of fish oil alone or fish oil in combination with probiotics cross-sectionally; this occurred not only when the children were aged 6 months but was also evident longitudinally from one year up to 5–6 years of age. This is evidence that the offspring's metabolic profile can be modulated through the mother's diet, which may also explain the clinical findings shown previously (11,12). These findings suggest that children of mothers with overweight and obesity may benefit from a dietary intervention with fish oil. However, further research will be needed to translate these interesting observations on metabolomics into clinically meaningful outcomes in children.

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KL, VH designed research; KL, NH, and JV conducted research; DM analyzed data; LL and TV supervision of analysis; VH, DM, KL, NH and CZ interpreted results; VH drafted manuscript; VH, NH, LS, DM, KL wrote the paper; KL supervision and project administration. All authors reviewed and commented on the paper KL had primary responsibility for final content. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Data Sharing Plan

The datasets are not available due to the fact that they contain information that could compromise the privacy and consent of the participants.

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Conflicts of Interest

None of the authors declares conflict of interest.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

None.

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Table 1. Characteristics of mothers and children according to the intervention groups.

	Total n	All	Group n	Fish oil + placebo	Probiotics + placebo	Fish oil + probiotics	Placebo + placebo	p- value ¹
MOTHER BASELINE:								
Mother's age (years)	300	30.6 (4.9)	78/71/74/77	30.6 (4.9)	31.1. (4.2)	31.0 (4.6)	30.5 (4.2)	0.8
Education (college or university education) (n (%))¹	300	194 (65.0)	78/71/74/77	54 (69.0)	47 (66.0)	45 (61.0)	48 (62.0)	0.7
Primipara (n (%))¹	300	154 (51.0)	78/71/74/77	43 (55.0)	37 (52.0)	36 (49.0)	38 (49.0)	0.8
Smoking before pregnancy (n (%))¹	300	50 (17.0)	78/71/74/77	7 (9.0)	17 (24.0)	6 (8.1)	20 (26.0)	0.002
Prepregnancy BMI (kg/m²)²	300	28.6 (26.4, 31.8)	78/71/74/77	29.4 (27.3, 32.9)	27.8 (26.4, 30.3)	28.3 (25.8, 31.4)	29.0 (26.4, 31.7)	0.12
Obesity and overweight (n (%))	300		78/71/74/77					0.2
with overweight (25 ≤ BMI < 30)¹		185 (62.0)		41 (53.0)	49 (69.0)	47 (64.0)	48 (62.0)	
with obesity (BMI ≥ 30)¹		115 (38.0)		37 (47.0)	22 (31.0)	27 (36.0)	29 (38.0)	
MOTHER PREGNANCY:								
Smoking during pregnancy (n (%))¹	298	9 (3.0)	78/70/73/77	0 (0.0)	1 (1.4)	3 (4.1)	5 (6.5)	0.09
GDM diagnosis (n (%))¹	294	25 (32.0)	77/71/71/75	25 (32.0)	21 (30.0)	19 (27.0)	21 (28)	0.9
Gestational weeks at the delivery (weeks)²	300	39.9 (39.0, 40.6)	78/71/74/77	39.9 (39.3, 40.4)	40.1 (39.0, 40.7)	39.9 (39.0, 40.7)	39.7 (38.6, 40.6)	0.7
Vaginal delivery (n (%))¹	300	251 (84.0)	78/71/74/77	65 (83.0)	59 (83.0)	62 (84.0)	66 (86.0)	>0.9
CHILD BIRTH:								
Girl sex (n (%))¹	299	149 (50.0)	77/71/74/77	40 (52.0)	33 (46.0)	42 (57.0)	34 (44.0)	0.4
Born preterm (< 37+0 gw) (n (%))¹	300	17 (5.7)	78/71/74/77	4 (5.1)	4 (5.6)	7 (9.5)	2 (2.6)	0.3
Birth weight (g)²	300	3,620 (3,295, 3,975)	78/71/74/77	3,633 (3,325, 3,920)	3,610 (3,275, 4,005)	3,620 (3,300, 3,980)	3,600 (3,290, 3,990)	>0.9
Birth height (cm)²	195	51.0 (49.0, 52.0)	76/71/71/77	51.0 (50.0, 51.3)	51.0 (49.5, 52.0)	51.0 (49.0, 52.0)	51.0 (49.0, 52.0)	>0.9
Birth head circumference (cm)¹	196	35.0 (34.0, 36.5)	76/71/70/77	35.3 (34.5, 36.0)	35.5 (34.0, 3.5)	35.0 (34.0, 36.0)	35.0 (34.0, 36.0)	0.9

BMI, body mass index; cm, centimeters; g, grams; GDM, gestational diabetes mellitus; gw, gestational weeks; kg/m², kilograms per square meter; n, number of samples; mo, months

¹One-way ANOVA for normally distributed continuous variables; Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test for non-normally distributed continuous variables; Pearson's Chi-squared test or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables.

²Categorical data expressed as frequency (%); continuous non-normally distributed data expressed as median (interquartile range), otherwise continuous normally distributed data expressed as mean (standard deviation).

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Flowchart of the present study of children with available serum sample for nuclear magnetic resonance determined metabolomics analysis.

Figure 2. Principal component analysis (PCA) plot of the metabolites of children at 6 months of age (a), 1 year of age (b), 2 years of age (c) and 5–6 years of age (d) according to the intervention groups. Metabolite data is log₁₀ transformed followed by Z-transformation with Euclidean distance. Large VLDL, L-VLDL; very large VLDL, XL-VLDL; extremely large VLDL, XXL-VLDL; free cholesterol, FC; phospholipids, PL; triacylglycerols, TG; to total lipids ratio, ratio.

Figure 3. MOFA2 multi-group framework analysis explaining the variability (a) in each intervention group at 6 months of age, 1 year of age, 2 years of age and 5–6 years of age. Figure shows the total explained variance of concentrations of metabolites (a), the explained variance of concentrations of metabolites in Factor 1 (b) and the weights of associated top 10 concentrations of metabolites per visit explaining variability in Factor 1 (c).

Figure 4. Heatmap of the effect size (normalized log₂ fold by median absolute deviation) of significantly changed concentration of serum metabolites of 6-month-old children in comparison between the intervention groups, maternal intake of fish oil+placebo (n=63), fish oil+probiotics (n=65) probiotics+placebo (n=59), and placebo+placebo (n=70) supplementation. * FDR > 0.05 ** FDR > 0.001 *** FDR > 0.0001 **** FDR > 0.00001. Docosahexaenoic acid, DHA; cholesterol in very large HDL, XL-HDL-C; cholesteryl esters in very large HDL, XL-HDL-CE; free cholesterol in very large HDL, XL-HDL-FC; total lipids in very large HDL, XL-HDL-L; phospholipids in very large HDL, XL-HDL-PL.

Figure 5. Interaction between the maternal intervention and time on the concentrations of serum metabolites of children. Only the metabolites that differed statistically significantly between the intervention groups at 6 months were chosen for this analysis. Generalized linear mixed model adjusted for child sex, maternal BMI and smoking.

Figures

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

PCA loadings

Effect Positive Negative

Supplementary figure 1

Supplementary figure 2